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**ASPECTS OF PREVENTION CORRUPTION IN UNIVERSITIES
OF MINISTRY OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS OF UKRAINE**

One of the significant obstacles to obtaining quality education is corruption. It serves as a factor that hinders the possibility of self-realization of talented young people, demotivates young people in personal growth, cultivates corruption ideology, discredits the value of education, creates distrust in society in the legal order of the state [1, p. 4]. This becomes even more relevant when applicants for higher education are future law enforcement officers - cadets, students of universities of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine with specific training conditions, who are trained in the conditions of armed aggression of the Russian Federation.

Two completely different aspects of combating corruption in universities of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine can be identified:

Aspect №1. To provide the employees of the universities of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine (hereinafter referred to as the MIA of Ukraine) with conditions that make honest and impeccable work more profitable than bribery and extortion. It is assumed that at first an employee of a universities of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine receives a fairly modest salary, but with the time of his honest work, more and more new material incentives appear. For example, the salary (financial support) is increased, there is the right to receive an interest-free loan for housing, leasing, a decent pension after retirement.

Aspect No. 2. Application of harsh punitive measures. An employee of a universities of the MIA of Ukraine, who knows that in the worst case he will receive a year of probation, and in most cases he will be able to simply be dismissed from his position, to pay off, sees bribery as a very attractive way to enrich himself.

It can be argued that there is an urgent need to create a decisive systemic action to create a special atmosphere of rejection of corruption, the atmosphere of rejection of the very essence of the manifestations of such a phenomenon in departmental education, especially in wartime.

Combating corruption in education should be carried out by different actors at different levels. In addition to state bodies, the educational and scientific community, the management, the Academic Council and the cadet and student self-government of the universities of the MIA of Ukraine.

Let us highlight the measures aimed at preventing and combating corruption in the educational sphere:

1. Increasing the value of higher education, as well as the quality of education (this will affect not only the corruption component in higher education, but will also significantly improve the training of specialists who will graduate from the MIA of Ukraine).

2. Increasing responsibility for corrupt activities, while the quality of social protection of teachers should also be improved. Minimizing the involvement of instructors and administrative staff in corrupt practices is associated with: improving their remuneration; strengthening the means of deterrence through the creation of a system of official investigations of corruption cases and making management decisions based on their results; principled position of the administrations of the universities of the MIA of Ukraine. It is important to interest the cadet in the subject and specialty, to explain the vocation of the profession; to introduce new forms of activating the role of the cadet in acquiring knowledge; to improve the level of teaching.

3. Strict legislative ban on the provision of «services» for writing essays, term papers, dissertations and theses.

4. Introduction of a system of external evaluation of cadets' knowledge, using the already established state procedure of external independent evaluation, along with the improvement of internal evaluation criteria and encouragement of cadets to acquire real knowledge during the educational process, as well as the introduction of impersonal forms of testing and examination.

5. Active public discussion (in particular, in social networks, messengers) of individual cases of bribery and abuse of office for personal gain, as well as the dissemination of assessments of the overall level of corruption in certain educational institutions.

6. Increasing transparency and accountability of universities of the MIA of Ukraine both to the community of the educational institution and to society as a whole [2, www].

7. Application of educational measures (organizational, patriotic, information-propaganda, legal, cultural, educational and social) [3, p. 7]. In the conditions of war, it is necessary to highlight patriotic education, which is aimed at the formation and development of national consciousness and civic responsibility, professionally important qualities and cultural abilities in young people.

Therefore, the following statement will be true: cadets who have passed through the system of education in the MIA of Ukraine, which will have signs of corruption, will further use these principles of corruption in their lives and practical activities, consider them a normal means of solving cases, teach their children, thereby creating a kind of vicious circle in the state and society.

The overcoming of corruption will contribute to the further development of Ukraine as a civilized European country and our soonest Victory.

References

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ЩОДО СТВОРЕННЯ ЄДИНОГО РЕЄСТРУ ПОВІДОМЛЕНЬ ПРО КОРУПЦІЙНІ ТА ПОВ'ЯЗАНІ З КОРУПЦІЄЮ ДІЯННЯ

Нині інформаційний простір перевантажений. Значення та вплив інформації на всі процеси в суспільстві постійно зростає. Більшість людей мають гаджети, що дозволяють поширювати інформацію миттєво. Текстовий, аудіо та відео контент містить різну інформацію, в тому числі, й щодо корупції в Україні. Попри численні повідомлення в мережі інтернет про корупційні й пов'язані з корупцією діяння, негативну суспільну реакцію на неї та наявність низки державних органів, що протидіють корупції реалізувати таку інформацію вдається відносно рідко.

Вважаємо, перспективним є напрямок діджиталізації держави щодо отримання, накопичення та можливості обробки повідомлень про корупційні й пов'язані з корупцією діяння, зокрема, суб'єктів та схем. Нині кожен державний орган має свої джерела отримання інформації про корупцію. Проте, попри врегульовані в законодавстві процедури через низку причин, як-то латентності, сприйняття корупції, зневіри у можливість реакції з боку керівників відповідно до законодавства України, недовіри до державних інституцій та інших ситуація змінюється на краще повільно. Розуміння того, що будь-яке повідомлення про корупцію лишиться в базі даних довічно, а доступ до такої інформації будуть мати різні суб'єкти, в тому числі, й уповноважені розслідувати такі випадки і притягувати до відповідальності, вважаємо, може змінити ставлення до таких повідомлень як заявника так і суб'єктів, уповноважених проводити розслідування чи перевірки за отриманою інформацією.